

Summary

Sea ice plays an important role for the Arctic environment - floating ice influences Arctic ecosystems as well as global solar reflection and ocean and atmospheric circulation. As a consequence of global warming, the Arctic sea ice cover has reduced in extent and has shifted from predominantly multi-year to seasonal ice over the last couple of decades. The entire Arctic Ocean is now approaching a marginal ice zone (MIZ; extends between fast ice and open ocean and comprises a variety of different forms of ice) in the summer season, where surface waves play an increasingly important role.

Economical and geopolitical interest in the polar region combined with the withdrawal of the Arctic ice cover has led to increased human activity in the region. New shipping routes, exploitation of natural resources and research activities are some examples. Such activities raise the need for better wave forecasts in the MIZ to ensure safe operations. Therefore, improved physical understanding of atmosphere-ocean mechanisms, such as wave-ice interactions are important in the process of global circulation and climate models.

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Key Messages

- ⇒ Current wave forecasts lack validated understanding of how sea ice dampens waves, which is a scientific foundation needed to improve climate predictions.
- ⇒ A new ship-mounted wave measurements technique used in the Arctic marginal ice zone, which measured wave parameters achieved 80% accuracy (compared to the ERA5 spectral wave hindcast model) enabling better real-time forecasting.
- ⇒ Researchers used innovated underwater measurement systems, using remotely operated vehicles and specialized tracking techniques, creating new options for long-term Arctic Ocean monitoring.
- ⇒ Standard commercial acoustic testing, using the Doppler current velocimeter (ADCP) has been validated for measuring fine-scale ocean turbulence.
- ⇒ Field experiments on Svalbard, where a full-scale ice floe was towed back and forth to simulate wave motion, provides direct evidence of how these technologies perform in Arctic conditions and detailed information about sea-ice damping mechanisms.
- ⇒ Extensive observations confirmed that approximately 1/3 of the energy injected into the wave-ice simulation was dissipated in turbulence around the moving ice floe, which underpins the role of turbulence as an important wave damping mechanism. This provides concrete data for coastal protection planning and offshore infrastructure design.

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Background

Wave-ice interactions are key mechanisms for the polar regions. As the Arctic sea ice is declining, greater areas of open water appear. When the fetch (distance of which wind blows over the ocean) increases, larger and more energetic waves dominate the region and enhance the breakup of the Arctic ice cover in a positive feedback mechanism. On the other hand, the presence of sea ice dampens propagating waves. Several phenomena are known to attenuate waves in an ice floe field, such as wave scattering or directional spreading, collisions between neighboring ice floes, turbulence injected into the water around the ice and viscous dissipation in the boundary layer beneath the ice.

However, there is uncertainty associated with the dominating source of wave energy dissipation due to sea ice. The dissipated wave energy is absorbed in the ocean and affects atmosphere-ocean energy transfer and global ocean circulations and ultimately the climate. Therefore, it is important to gain knowledge into the details of dissipation processes to improve wave forecasts and climate models.

More field measurements and direct observations are required to validate both mathematical models and remote sensing such as satellite or airborne altimeter data, which are used in forecasting. The harsh conditions and inaccessibility of the Arctic makes it a challenging place to work in-situ. Consequently, there are relatively few field experiments on wave propagation in ice, especially considering the vast extension of the polar regions with the rich diversity of ice types and wave conditions. The development and validation of various field measurement techniques adapted to Arctic conditions has therefore been our primary focus.

The Science, Part I: New Measurement Techniques

Two experimental techniques have been introduced to the wave-ice scientific community. The first methodology is a ship-mounted wave measurement device presented in Løken et al. (2021a), which consists of an ultrasonic range meter (UG) and an inertial motion unit (IMU) to correct for ship motion, both mounted in the bow of a research vessel, as shown in Fig. 1. The setup was tested in the Arctic marginal ice zone (MIZ) and validated against pre-deployed wave buoys. A great advantage of the ship mounted instrument is that it can gather data continuously and autonomously during expeditions, without dedicating expensive work time or equipment to perform the measurements. The measurement setup consists of affordable, open-source components (Rabault et al., 2020), which can be mounted on any ship.

Figure 1. Schematic of the bow-mounted wave measurement device, correcting for ship motion

Turbulence is one of the attenuation mechanisms in wave-ice interactions. Turbulence measurements require detailed information about water kinematics, which is usually obtained with particle image velocimetry (PIV). This is a technique that conventionally requires a large and expensive laser, which is inconvenient to deploy in a wave-in-ice environment. The second measurement technique introduced in this research is a PIV setup designed for field use under Arctic conditions, presented and validated in a laboratory wave tank in Løken et al. (2021b). It consists of a BlueROV2 remotely operated vehicle (ROV) that is maneuvered below the ice to record an array of rising bubbles used as tracing particles (see Fig. 2). Hence, the methodology is referred to as *ROV-bubble PIV*. Bubbles are advantageous in the sense that they approximately rise in a 2D plane and passively follow the water flow, which makes a light or laser sheet redundant, but it is of course necessary to correct for the vertical buoyant bubble velocity to ultimately obtain the water 2D velocity field. The methodology offers the possibility of investigating water kinematics around water-ice and ice-ice interactions with a temporal and spatial resolution that extends beyond conventional acoustic instruments.

Figure 2. Schematic of the ROV-bubble system in an Arctic environment. From Løken et al. (2021b).

In addition to the ROV-bubble system, an acoustic Doppler current profiler (ADCP) has been used to measure turbulence properties in this research. The instrument was operated in *high resolution* mode, which is a relatively new technology that enables turbulence measurements on a much smaller scale than

what is found in, e.g., a tidal channel or river where ADCPs are usually deployed. A validation study was performed under controlled conditions in a towing tank laboratory to test the instrument's ability to resolve small-scale turbulence (Løken et al. 2024).

The Science, Part 2: Field Experiments on the Ice

The concluding work of this research is summarized in Løken et al. (2022). A field laboratory was constructed on the sea ice of the van Mijen fjord in Svalbard to investigate and directly observe mechanisms that contribute to attenuation of waves in the interaction with ice. A full-scale ice floe was cut out and set into motion by electrical winches to simulate wave motion and naturally occurring floe-floe collisions (see left panel of Fig. 3). Consequently, water was pumped into the depth, creating turbulence around the floe (visualized by the bubble tracers in the right panel of Fig. 3). Different wave damping mechanisms were studied with various sensors (IMU, ROV-bubble, ADCP, etc.), which allowed for comparison of the energy input rate with dissipation rates related to energy loss.

Figure 3. Arctic field laboratory set up for simulation of wave-ice interactions. Left: The ice floe is pulled by winches to simulate wave-induced motion (the ROV is in the water). Right: An ice-ice collision injects a turbulent eddy into the water (seen from ROV).

Ice-ice interactions is a well-known mechanism that contributes to wave attenuation in the MIZ. However, the rate of absorbed energy in the ice-ice collisions was found to be approximately 8% of the total input energy rate. On the other hand, a larger portion of the energy was transferred from the moving ice floe

to the water in the form of turbulence. The rate of turbulent kinetic energy dissipated in the water was estimated to be approximately 37% of the total input energy rate.

Implications

Previously, scholars in the wave-ice community disagree about the effect of turbulence as a wave damping mechanism in the MIZ, and no clear consensus had been reached regarding the dominating ice-related wave attenuation processes. A central working hypothesis in this research was that a significant part of the attenuated wave energy in the interaction with ice is dissipated in turbulence. It was found through empirical observations that more than 1/3 of the input energy rate dissipates in turbulence in the water around the ice floe. This result provides evidence that turbulence is a substantial wave damping mechanism in the MIZ under certain conditions. This research sheds new light on a critical scientific uncertainty that has limited the accuracy of models and forecasting systems.

However, caution should be exercised in generalizing the findings to all wave-ice interactions, as many variables are involved and the MIZ in a complex environment. This research also highlights the need for more direct observations of wave damping processes in the MIZ to strengthen our physical understanding of the mechanisms at play. The validated measurements can provide reliable tools for ongoing Arctic monitoring and risk assessment.

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